

CONDOLENCE AS A FORM OF ENGLISH SPEECH ETIQUETTE AND IT'S EXPRESSION IN LETTERS

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The purpose of this article is to deal with discourse of condolence as a form of English speech etiquette. Relevance of training speech etiquette forms in the situation of condolence is increased in conditions of modeling real communicative situations. The paper as well as discusses the ways of expressing condolences via letters.

Key words: condolences, speech etiquette, discourse, letter, sympathy, communication

Modern intercultural communication makes certain requirements for mastering the norms of speech etiquette in the language of international communication - English. Possession of speech etiquette implies the observance of a number of rules of communicative behavior. Language is inseparable from culture and the ethnic group in which the person is located. This state of affairs imposes certain limits not only on native speakers, but, first of all, on people of a different culture. The language preserves and transmits cultural values not only in various forms of written and oral speech, but also in the vision of the world, the mentality and traditions of the people. Language always exists within a culture, not outside it. Thus, the problems of intercultural communication come to the fore in modern science.

The relevance of the study of this topic is to increase the effectiveness of teaching English by modeling a real communicative situation of condolences.

In modern times, it is difficult to imagine that language performs only one task - the transmission of a message, i.e. its informative function. New communication conditions leave their mark on the participants in a conversation or letter. Now the language must be learned on the basis of knowledge about the world and culture of the peoples of the language being studied and in an inseparable unity with them. The effectiveness and efficiency of foreign language proficiency can be measured not only by excellent knowledge of grammar and understanding of certain information from the text, but by mastering and mastering the rules of etiquette, as well as the conditions and culture of communication.

The problems of intercultural communication are given an increasing place in the scientific research of modern scientists [2].

S. G. Ter-Minasova identifies the following components of culture, which carry a nationally specific color:

- 1) traditions (stable elements of culture) and customs;
- 2) traditional household culture;
- 3) everyday behavior (communication norms);
- 4) "national pictures of the world" (perception of the surrounding world depending on the national characteristics of thinking);
- 5) artistic culture [2].

The sociocultural factor plays an indispensable role in learning a foreign language. Any important social phenomenon is reflected in writing and in speech. Each language serves the society where it is used as a mother tongue. Above we are already mentioned that the components of the culture of a society consist of many terms, thus, we can conclude that the importance of language in any culture cannot be overestimated.

Basic rules of speech etiquette in society always affect the norms of communication and behavior adopted in a given culture. There are always rules that govern this or that situation and communication. In some cases they will be tougher, in others less so.

In European culture, the attitude towards death has always been unambiguously negative, and was perceived very sadly. It is believed that the deceased will leave with all honors and the corresponding rituals will be performed by his relatives and relatives, who, in turn, can also count on the help and support of loved ones [5]. Thus, the first thing to do in this situation is to offer condolences.

Condolence can be considered as a certain communicative act, which, it seems, belongs to the category of expressive ones.

Expressive speech acts include those in which the speaker expresses his feelings and attitude to what is happening [3.154]. The illocutionary goal of the expressive is to express the psychological state given by the condition regarding the state of affairs, defined within the propositional content. Exemplary predicates expressing a psychological state are thank, congratulate, condole and others ([3.158]. J. Searle calls such speech acts are polite, because through them the speaker shows his attention to the interlocutor, informing that he is seen, respected, loved, sympathized.

A. Vezhbtskaya refers the verbs of this list to class of behaviors, or calls them verbs of etiquette behavior [1.269].

For the first time, the term "behabitive" was introduced by J. Austin, who attributed to this group verbs expressing a reaction to the behavior of other people. According to A. Vezhbitskaya, the verb expressing the etiquette behavior of condolences is interpreted as follows:

"Please accept my condolences = I knew that something bad happened to you (someone close to you died), assuming that you are unhappy because of this, wanting to make sure that you know that I am also unhappy because of this, I say: "I am also unhappy because of this"[1, p. 270]

In speech genre condolence the following verbs- behabitives are used:

«To offer sympathy»; «To be sorry to hear»; «To extend sympathy»; «To be saddened»; «To express sympathy»; «To accept condolences \ sympathy» etc.; «To feel grief»; «To send my condolences»; «To offer condolences»; «To share grief»; «To be shocked at death»; «To relief the pain»; «To be with you in the loss»[5].

The condolence illocution correlates, thus way, with the expressions of the following psychological states, emotions and feelings of the speaker (addresser): «Sympathy»; «Sadness»; «Grief»; «Shock»; «Pain»; «Sorrow»; «Being floored»; «Missing him\ her» [5].

Addressee of condolences addressed to illocution of this speech act, presumably experiences the following set of psychological states, emotions, feelings, which are called perlocutionary effect: consolation, loss, wonderful memories, shock, pain, deep grief (directly opposite emotional states, for example, joy, are excluded):

- « I join with so many others who knew Jack in offering our deepest sympathy on his passing. It is little consolation at this sad time, it should be of some satisfaction to know that in his passing you can celebrate the end of a very long and productive life».

- «You find peace and comfort in knowing that his loss is felt by all who knew and loved him».

- «I know firsthand how profound a loss it is when you realize that he will no longer be there for all the events in your life. I can tell you though that the very best way to mark his passing is by filling your mind with all of the wonderful memories you have of happier times».

-«There are no words to describe the utter grief that I am feeling right now. I cannot possibly imagine the shock and sorrow that has been thrust on your family as well».

- «There is no good time or way for someone you care about to die. I am sorry to find out that your dad's brother is making this even more painful for you and for your brothers».

- «It's so sad when someone so young departs from us. I know how close you and your brother were and I can only imagine the depth of your sorrow».

- «His brief life blessed you in many ways, and his absence will leave a horrible void in your lives. How your hearts must ache for him»![5].

Condolence is a performative act since the illocutionary force of the utterance is revealed in it with the help of an illocutionary verb in the appropriate form (present tense, first person, singular, indicative, active voice) – the performative form (2). Such performative verbs are to condole, to be sorry. There are also a wide variety of designs V+N:

-«I'm very sorry to hear about the loss of your grandfather».

-«I just heard about your dad. I am so sorry and wanted to offer my condolences».

-«I am so sorry and I want you to know I am thinking of you and what you and your family must be going through right now».

- «I'm sorry I never had a chance to meet your mother, although we spoke on the phone several times»

-«There is no good time or way for someone you care about to die and I am sorry to find out that your dad's brother is making this even more painful for you and for your brothers»

- «I am truly sorry to hear of your recent loss of your dad»

- «I was so sorry to hear of Ann's death»

- «I don't know what to say Brad, except that I'm so, so sorry to hear about the death of your mom»

- «I am sorry to find out that your mom's brother is making this even more painful for you and for your brother»

An important feature of the forms of expressing condolences is that the speech act and its implementation in speech coincide, hence the use of the present tense forms:

-«I want you to know that my thoughts are with you during this difficult time»

- «Jenny and I grieve with you in the loss of your child»

- «I know mere words may offer but little comfort at this tragic time, but know that my deepest feelings of sympathy lie with you and your family»

-«I am very sorry that he is no longer with you»

- «I don't know what to say Brad, except that I'm so, so sorry to hear about the death of your mom»
 - «I know how close you and your brother were and I can only imagine the depth of your sorrow»
 - «I want you to know that I'm here for you and your family»
 - «I extend my sincere sympathy to all of you at what I know is a very sad and mournful time»
 - «I pray that you will have the strength you need to get through this very difficult time. My thoughts and prayers are with you and your wonderful family»
- [5].

Thus, condolence is a speech act or a communicative act that embodies the unity of locution, illocution and perlocution (the resulting state: experiencing grief, loss, misfortune, etc.)

Let us turn to the structure of the text of the letter of condolence, its purpose is always to express one's compassion and comfort the mourners. The expression of directly opposite emotions and feelings is not acceptable by the rules of etiquette and moral standards of society, no one will write about joy and delight. An important aspect of any letter is its informational content and saturation. A letter of condolence can be attributed to one-dimensional letters, since one aspect of such a letter is its entire content and does not require a response from the addressee. The addressee may enter into correspondence with the addressee, but the rules of etiquette and the current situation do not require an immediate response. Such a letter is not always without emotional coloring combined with conciseness. It is not customary to talk too much about any unpleasant moments in a person's life.

From the point of view of the compositional structure, the discourse containing formulas for expressing condolences is a letter in which one can select the following elements. Here you can define that the letter has a closed structure, which includes such structural components as: an appeal, a motive, the actual words of condolence, an offer of help, and a signature. And the content of the text becomes clear that the part of the letter dedicated to the deceased and his deeds during his lifetime is the most vivid and descriptive. There are not so many references to the mourners themselves, such epithets as "strong", "nervous", the phrases "strength of character", "sense of pride" are used. They indicate their emotional state and how they should be, in order to cope with grief.

The offer of help, as we can see, can be different, and include both material and non-material things and benefits. Such a letter is often personal in nature, so the parts into which it is divided are always fewer than if it were a business letter. The discourse of condolences can contain both implicit and explicit forms of expression. Implicit ones include an offer of help, since it is traditionally “so accepted” by the norms of etiquette, to offer help, thereby condoling. To explicit, directly, the very expression of condolences.

Thus, the analysis showed that speech etiquette is an important component of interpersonal communication, the observance of the rules and norms of which is a requirement of modern intercultural communication, the relevance of studying which, in turn, acquires unprecedented importance in a modern multicultural society.

Knowledge of the etiquette of behavior has always been highly valued by a person, especially in such non-routine cases as death. Thoughts of the death of a close relative or friend are always avoided, it is natural and often takes you by surprise. A condolence is expected to be ready to share the grief, to support the mourner with a personal presence or memory of the deceased, to give his time. Material, physical or organizational assistance is welcome.

In many European countries, it has been customary to respond in writing to the death of a person since the 18th century. An acceptable means of expressing condolences is a letter, since it is not always possible to convey your words orally. The reason for writing such a letter is unpleasant, therefore its content is conveyed in essence, without idle talk and tactlessness. A large number of words describing good deeds and deeds during the life of the deceased are present in a letter written in his honor.

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